

A PFHS (Precipitation from Homogeneous Solutions) Method for the Gravimetric Estimation of Gallium(III) and Indium(III)

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IN earlier communications¹⁻³ from this laboratory, benzoic acid and its derivatives have been successfully used for the gravimetric estimations of gallium(III) and indium(III). During recent years the homogeneous precipitation of metal ions by the addition of a suitable buffer solution of pH just sufficient to precipitate the required hydroxide produces an easily filtrable precipitate and the new technique of PFHS has since been developed and utilized for the estimation of aluminium⁴. The present communication deals with the modifications of the methods reported earlier by developing PFHS method for the gravimetric estimations of Ga(III) and In(III).

Experimental

Stock solutions of gallium(III) and indium(III) were prepared and standardised as described earlier¹⁻³.

Precipitating reagent: A buffer solution of pH 4.25 was prepared by dissolving 4.5 g of ammonium chloride, 5 g of benzoic acid and 15 g of ammonium benzoate in 2 litre of deionised water.

Procedure: Aliquot quantities of gallium(III) or indium(III) chloride solutions were taken, diluted to 50 ml and neutralized with dilute aqueous ammonia till a faint permanent cloudiness was observed which was removed by a careful dropwise addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. 30 ml of benzoate buffer solution was added to this clear solution which was then boiled for 2 min and allowed to stand for 40 min on a water bath when a white granular precipitate gradually settled down. The precipitate was filtered through a quantitative fluted filter paper (Whatman No. 44), washed with 2% ammonium benzoate solution, dried at 110°, ignited to M₂O₃ (M = Ga³⁺ or In³⁺), cooled and weighed.

Though a large number of experiments had been done to find the optimum conditions for complete precipitation viz., the effect of pH, time for digestion etc., yet for the sake of brevity the results obtained for the estimation of gallium(III) and indium(III) by this modified method at pH 4.5 only are discussed.

The standard deviation σ_e and standard error σ_m have been evaluated for a set of eight identical samples using the formulae

$$\sigma_e = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_1)^2 - \sum_n(\bar{x})^2}{(n-1)}} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_m = \frac{\sigma_e}{n}$$

and are given in Table I. The low values of σ_m depict that the developed PFHS methods for the

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estimation of these metals are certainly better than the ordinary precipitation method.

TABLE I—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF Ga³⁺ AND In³⁺, BY (A) PFHS METHOD AND (B) BASIC BENZOATE METHOD

Ga₂O₃ taken = 112.60 mg; In₂O₃ taken = 98.40 mg.

S.No.	Parameter evaluated	Gallium(III)		Indium(III)	
		Method A	Method B	Method A	Method B
1.	Average value for M ₂ O ₃ mgs for eight samples ($\bar{x}$)	112.55	112.38	98.42	98.26
2.	Standard deviation σ_e	3.614	4.277	3.420	6.655
3.	Standard error σ_m	0.452	0.535	0.427	0.832

The new procedures were further tested for the estimation of these metals in presence of many common foreign ions and it is possible to estimate Ga³⁺ and In³⁺ in presence of excess of Na⁺ and NH₄⁺ and equivalent amounts of Ca²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Mn²⁺ ions which are not precipitated under these conditions. However, a small fraction Co²⁺, Be²⁺ and Fe²⁺ gets co-precipitated in the first precipitation which is overcome by dissolving the precipitate in dilute hydrochloric acid and the subsequent reprecipitation of Ga³⁺ and In³⁺ by the usual procedure and thus removing adsorbed ions.

References

1. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and D. C. RUPAINWAR, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 100.
2. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and D. C. RUPAINWAR, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 103.
3. T. N. SRIVASTAVA and N. SINGH, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, 27, 164.
4. R. J. IRVING, *Talanta*, 1967, 14, 1349.

Studies on Lebbekinin E, A New Saponin from *Albizzia lebbek* Benth.

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ALBIZZIA lebbek Benth. commonly known as "Siris" belongs to the family Leguminosae. Varshney *et al.*¹⁻⁴ have studied the various parts of this tree and isolated four new saponins named as Lebbekinin A, B, C and D.

The bark of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth from U.P. has also been studied by Varshney *et al.*⁵ and reported to contain a saponin of acacic acid.